

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Teaching physical education during the time of pandemic

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Abstract

This research study aimed to identify the modalities used in teaching Physical Education in the district of San Rafael, Bulacan during the time of pandemic. Further, the study investigated the challenges experienced by the Physical Education (PE) teachers and the solutions they made to address these challenges. The end goal of the study was a school action plan for physical education to address the issues in teaching PE during the pandemic. Qualitative research design through thematic analysis was employed and a semi structured virtual interview was conducted to further substantiate the findings of the study. Results revealed that modular learning is the most common modality used by Physical Education teachers in this time of pandemic. Other modalities such as synchronous and asynchronous online learning and physical activity mobile applications were used by the teachers. It was also revealed that their main reason for using the modalities was for the welfare of their students. Further, the lack of resources of students in terms of internet connectivity and gadgets was the common struggle experienced by the Physical Education teachers and the most common solution done by the Physical Education teachers was doing follow-up with the students through social media. This study recommended the implementation of the proposed action plan to improve the modalities of teachers in teaching Physical Education and to help them avoid problems they may encounter.

Keywords: Modalities in teaching physical education; Modular learning; Distance learning; Challenges

1. Introduction

The educational system in the country and around the world was severely affected by the COVID-19 pandemic which began in December 2019. It became a worldwide health crisis where everyone was literally affected regardless of age, gender, and social status. Due to this, most countries closed schools, colleges, and universities to contain the spread of the virus. The crisis became a dilemma not only to the health sectors but also to the education sectors. When the Philippine government ordered closures of all educational institutions, the disruptions were unexpected since classes were still running (Ancheta & Ancheta, 2020). After months of lockdown, countries like Spain, New Zealand, Thailand, and Iran began to ease their quarantine restrictions after a decrease in infections (Secon et al., 2020). For almost two pandemic months, most countries around the world have temporarily closed educational institutions to contain the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic and reduce infections (UNESCO, 2020). This closure has affected more than 1.2 billion learners worldwide with more than 28 million learners in the Philippines (UNESCO, 2020). The Department of Education initiated an innovative and resourceful delivery of quality, accessible, relevant, and liberating education to all Filipino learners amidst the pandemic. At the basic education, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP), which took effect in School Year 2020-2021 and classes started last August 24, 2020, instead of June 2020. Thus, different modalities in learning were suggested by the Department of Education to deliver quality education to students.

The different modalities are modular distance learning, online distance learning, TV-Video/Radio-based Instruction and Blended Distance Learning (Deped Memo 162, s. 2020). Of the four (4) modalities, modular distance learning is the

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frequently applied modality in public schools. This is because modules were more accessible to be used by the students than participating in an online learning class and reproduction of modules was more feasible. Further, modules are portable and can be delivered to the barangays where the students live. Using modules helped our educational system to deliver quality education the students need in this time of pandemic. But it may not engage students in learning, especially in Physical Education. Modules had no interaction between a student and teacher, there were no audio/visual elements that help students to be engaged in learning and required the reading skills of the students. Moreover, according to Dale's Cone of Experience, students only remember 10% of what they read which is exemplified by using modules. Using verbal and visual symbols is the least effective method (Dale, 1969). According to Mart (2011), "without relevant student's engagement, new material cannot be learned or mastered." Thus, the learning of students is greatly compromised due to disengagement in using modules. Students with low levels of engagement hardly gain engagement without intervention (Archambault & Dupere, 2016). Teachers should ensure that students are engaged in the learning process to maximize each student's learning and development and to prevent gradual disengagement, school failure or dropout (Havik & Westergard, 2018) in this time of revolution in education. Engaged children are empowered and it will lead to the desired academic achievements (Laukka, 2018). To alleviate the problems in using modules for learning, teachers of Physical Education used different modalities to deliver the lessons to students amidst the struggles of pandemic.

While a plethora of empirical studies on Physical Education deal mostly with its relationship on motivation, academic performance, and academic achievement abound in the literature, the need to investigate the modalities used in teaching Physical Education during the pandemic remains a research imperative, hence, this study. Further, this study focused on the current situation of pandemic that is revolutionizing the system of education. Also, the challenges and solutions encountered by Physical Education teachers were discussed in this study.

2. Methods

2.1. Research Design

The research employed qualitative research design. The process of research involves empirical work being carried out with the collection of data which can concur, refute or contest theories which in turn allows for understanding and clarification for different observations (May, 1997).

2.2. Participants

The study involved five (5) senior public high schools in San Rafael, Bulacan. These included Carlos F. Gonzales High School, Salapungan High School, San Rafael National Trade School, Lydia T. Villangca Trade School, and Maronquillo National High School. From each of these schools, two (2) Physical Education teachers from Senior High School participated in the study, one from Grade 11 and another from Grade 12. Since Maronquillo National High School only had one Physical Education teacher in Senior High School, the total number of participants was reduced to nine (9). All the nine (9) Physical Education teachers agreed to be interviewed virtually. Out of the nine (9) PE teachers in senior high school, six (6) were males and three (3) were females.

2.3. Research Instruments

2.3.1. Interview protocol

The researcher-made interview protocol served as the instrument used in gathering relevant data in this study. It contained three (3) guide questions which were used to elicit the experiences of the participants. The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCS) and modules given by the Department of Education were used as basis for the interview protocol.

2.3.2. Letter of consent

The researcher submitted a letter to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bulacan asking permission to conduct a study in San Rafael, Bulacan.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure

2.4.1. Permission from Schools Division Superintendent

The researcher submitted a letter to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Bulacan seeking permission for the conduct of the study in the five (5) schools in San Rafael District. Upon approval, the researcher asked

the school head from each school about the most convenient time the interview may be done with the teachers. The teaching time of the faculty members was not sacrificed because of the interview. Likewise, the learners' learning time was also considered in the conduct of the interview. The teachers had an individual virtual interview via Google Meet.

2.5. Ethical Considerations

Several ethical considerations were considered to ensure that the study was conducted in an appropriate manner. To comply with ethical considerations in conducting research, all participants were asked to give a written consent to be interviewed and to participate in the research. Then, the purpose of the research was explained to the participants, and they had the right to withdraw at any point during the interview. Permission to record the interview was also obtained from the participants.

2.5.1. Confidentiality and anonymity

The researcher made sure that the information gathered from each of the interviewees would be kept confidential. Their names were anonymous throughout the study.

2.5.2. Honesty and respect

The interviewees were treated with utmost respect as their answers were tape recorded. The researcher showed her honesty by asking all the respondents if she could record their virtual interview for proper data analysis.

2.6. Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

To process the qualitative data gathered through the interviews, thematic analysis was used in the study. Thematic analysis is the process of identifying patterns or themes within qualitative data (Maguire & Delahunt, 2017).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Interview Data

Table 1 Themes Generated from the Interviews

Theme 1. Mode of Delivery	
Subtheme A	Modular
Subtheme B	Online
Theme 2. Reasons	
Subtheme A	Student welfare
Subtheme B	Teacher convenience
Theme 3: Challenges	
Subtheme A	Personal (teacher & student)
Subtheme B	Logistics
Subtheme C	Performance and Assessment
Theme 4: Solutions	
Subtheme A	Personal
Subtheme B	Pedagogical
Subtheme C	Social (Parent involvement)

The interview with the participants were transcribed verbatim and were analyzed fully to look for significant statements, formulate their meanings, and classify them based on the researcher's understanding.

The significant information gathered from the data were scrutinized to form key words and phrases that fell into emergent themes. Using the researcher's own exact words, the researcher came up with the analysis of the modalities in teaching Physical Education in the time of pandemic.

All unnecessary data gathered from the verbatim dialogue that were unrelated and non-significant were set aside. The significant findings directly quoted from the respondent's responses to the guide questions were used and analyzed. All the useful information taken pertaining to the modalities in teaching Physical Education were taken.

3.1.1. Modular learning

The main modality used by the teachers in delivering the lessons to the students was using modules because this was the modality that was accessible and convenient to most students in the public schools. All of them (n=9) used modules as means of teaching Physical Education. These modules came from the Central Office and were distributed to the schools. These modules were placed in a *sisidlan* (bag) and given to the students in a scheduled basis. T2 shared how his school distributed the modules to their students.

"Nagbibigay po kami ng module every two weeks. Pinapasagutan po sa bata." (We give the modules every two weeks. The students will answer it.)

Though the Central Office should provide copies of the modules, that was not the case in other schools. T1 said that maybe because of their population, there were not enough modules to supply their school. As replacement for modules, teachers make learning activity sheets that were based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies given by DepEd. She said:

"Actually wala kaming nareceive na module for PE. Siguro dahil na din sa population namin. So ang ginawa ko is activity sheets or LAS. Yung activity sheets nagagawa ko siya through following the MELCS na binigay ng DepED and sa mga module from the other regions. Pinapattern ko lang siya dun, hindi ko kinokopya lahat." (Actually, we did not receive modules for PE. So, what I did was activity sheets or LAS. I can do the activity sheets by following the MELCS that was given by DepED and through the modules from the other regions. I pattern it from there, but I am not copying everything.)

T3, another teacher from a school which has no supply of modules, shared how he did his learning activity sheets. He said that he had a hard time looking for modules for Grade 12. So, what he did was handouts or learning activity sheets.

"Actually, ngayon wala pa rin akong materials for Grade 12. Kasi may mga groups na ginawa din sa division natin nag-aask ako dun pero walang pumapansin. Sabi ko baka pwede kayo magshare about module for Grade 12 for 3rd quarter and 4th quarter, and then naghahanap din ako sa ibang mga divisions wala din akong makita. So parang ang remedy ko na lang is gumawa ng mga handouts or LAS (Learning Activity Sheet) kasi nagturo naman ako ng PE before sa Grade 12 talaga 'yung recreational activity 'yung will be the 'topic. So parang ang plano ko na lang is mag-create na lang ng mga handouts or LAS or presentation para ibigay sa kanila. Kasi as of now, talaga wala pa akong materials for them. Baka meron kayo ah, bigyan n'yo ko." (Actually, now, we still don't have materials for Grade 12. There were groups that were made by the Division, and I asked there but no one is giving me attention. I asked if they could share modules for Grade 12, for 3rd and 4th quarter. I also searched modules on the other divisions but still, I cannot find anything. So, what I did was I created handouts or LAS (Learning Activity Sheet). I have taught PE in Grade 12 before, and recreational activity is the topic. So, my plan is to create handouts for them. If you have, share it with me.)

Though module is the main modality for students to learn in this pandemic, it cannot provide everything that students need to learn. It can only be used by students who read well; learning can be effective if students already have an awareness of learning as a process of behavior change because of experience (Kristanto, 2017). Thus, Physical Education teachers explored other ways to teach students amidst the pandemic. T4 stated that for students to understand the lessons better, other strategies are needed. She said:

"So pagka po minsan aside from the module, para po mas maintindihan talaga pong syempre yearly iniimprove din natin, naghahanap ka pa rin ng other strategy. Kapag po wala talaga, let's say tingin mo maiintindihan ng bata kung mas makakakuha ka. Sometimes po "di ba meron naman tayong - pwede naman tayong kumuha sa net. So sometimes kahit mga pictures kumukuha ako sa net. 'Yung mga gano'n ma'am para mas maunawaan ng bata. Kasi minsan "di po ba ang mga bata kasi parang hindi na sila 'yung magreread talaga lalo na mahahabang explanation. So as much as possible ginagawa kong simple." (Sometimes aside from the module, so they can understand more, yearly we improve, we are still looking for other strategies. If there is none, let's say students can understand better if you can find something.

Sometimes, even pictures I get from the internet. Strategies like that so students can understand better. Because sometimes they will not read, even long explanations. So as much as possible, I make it simple.)

3.1.2. Online learning

Another modality of teachers in teaching Physical Education in this pandemic was online learning. It can be classified into two: synchronous and asynchronous.

T7 explained how she used synchronous online classes to motivate the students. She highlighted that she conducts synchronous online class even one or two students only join the class. She related:

“Actually, hindi ako gumagamit ng mga video presentations or yung mga asynchronous kasi usually ang ginagawa ko talaga is more on yung sa online. So either, lima, sampu, one on one, nag-oonline ako per section. Kahit nag-iisa siya, ahhh, inaano ko, ahhh tinitignan ko talaga palagi na dapat namimeet ko ang bata at nakikita nila na “ay si ma’am pala kahit nag-iisa ang estudyante, pinupush pa din na magturo.” Kasi by word of mouth, malalaman ng mga kaklase nila na si ma’am pala kahit isa na lang tinuturuan, nagpupush pa din kasi malaking motivation din yun sa bata, na nakikita nila na ang teacher is ano talaga interesado talagang magturo. Although nag-iisa sila, at least ginawa natin yung best na effort natin para madeliver natin yung lessons. And then siyempre, yung online class na nabanggit ko nga sayo, yun yung ginagamit ko, yung gumagamit ako ng mga Google Meet. Siyempre yun naman yung basic eh.” (Actually, I don’t use video presentations or asynchronous because what I usually do is more online. So, either there are five, ten, one on one, I do online classes per section. Even I only have one student, ahhh, I am, ahhh, I make it sure to meet the students. And they can see that “even if there is one student, this teacher always pushes to teach. Because by word of mouth, their classmate will know that this teacher will teach even if there is only one student. It is a great motivation for the students because they can see that their teachers in interested in teaching them. Although there is only one student, at least we made our best effort to deliver the lessons. And then of course, the online class I mentioned, that is what I use, I employ Google Meet. Of course, that’s the basic one.)

3.1.3. Asynchronous Online Learning

This was the modality that teachers used most of the time because it provides more flexibility and options for the students to learn. As supplementary for the distributed modules, teachers engaged in different modalities for the learning of the students. The modalities of teachers in asynchronous online learning were the use of videos, digitized copy of the modules, social media, online assessment tool, physical activity mobile applications and collaboration with teachers.

3.1.4. Videos

Teachers used videos to support the lessons in the modules. All of them mentioned that they employ videos as supplementary material. T1 said to cater to all the students, she sent downloaded videos to students to support the lessons in the module. She said:

“So maliban sa online class, mostly asynchronous yung ginagawa ko para kung kelan sila may net at resources, dun nila maaaccess yung lessons. Maliban sa activity sheets na binibigay ko sa kanila, may videos din ako na sinesend. Mga video lessons yun to support kung ano yung nakalagay sa module. Example, last sem, physical fitness ako sa kanila. So nagsend ako ng videos ng different exercises para mas maintindihan nila yung lessons.” (Aside from online class, mostly I apply asynchronous so that when they have net and resources, they can access the lessons. Apart from the activity sheets that I gave to them, I also send videos. That are video lessons to support what is discussed in the modules. Example, last sem, my topic is physical fitness. So, I sent videos of different exercises so that they can understand the lessons better.)

Further, T7, who teaches dance, stated that she recorded videos of her while dancing the different steps of a dance. While giving the steps to the students, she used the videos so that her students would understand how to perform the dance. She recalled:

“And then number two, ang ginawa ko din ay yung preparation of video, yung mga video presentation. Halimbawa sa dance, diba meron tayong mga dances na hindi naman talaga familiar sa students yung mga steps. So ang ginagawa ko ahmmm, binibigay ko sa kanila yung mga simple steps and then kinocollab ko na yung ano, yung mga steps na yun, gumagawa na ko, kinocombine ko na siya para mabuo yung mismong dance step. So from the steps and sa video na binibigay ko, dun sila nagfafollow. Para pag meron ako binigay sa kanila na, anong tawag dito, para sa performance nila, yun na lang ang gagamitin nila. So pwede’ng ang gamitin ng bata is individual na sariling idea nila or pwede yung ginagamit ko na video presentation. So doon nilalagay ko yung mga countings saka yung mga phasing ng bawat steps.” (And then number two,

I also did the preparation of video, video presentations. Example, in dance, we have dances that are not familiar with the students, the steps. So, what I do, ahmmmm, I give to them the simple steps and then I collaborate it with, the steps, I make, I combine it to complete the exact dance step. So, from the steps I give to them and the video I sent to them, they will follow from there. So that when I give to them, what you call that, for their performance, they will just use it. So, the students can use their individual ideas, or they can adapt from the video presentations that I use. In the video, I place the counting and the phasing of each step.)

3.1.5. Digitized copy of modules

All the (9) teachers also mentioned that they use the digitized copy of modules as supplementary material for the students. Because it was easier for the students to see due to the minimal internet data it needs, pictures help the students to learn. Some students preferred the digitized copy of the modules; thus, the picture of the modules was sent to them. T4 said that some of her students wanted to do the modules earlier and they don't want to wait for the distribution of *sisidlan* (bags). She said:

"Opo, through sisidlan din po. Tapos po may mga bata po kasi na mas prefer nila na maagang gumawa pero ang ginagawa ko po 'yung personal na. Since mag-friend naman kami kaysa 'yung may idle time sila, mas gusto nila na gawin na, kaya sinesend ko na lang po. Tiyatiyagain mo talaga, ma'am. Tapos 'yun pong mga iba na wala talagang pang-download, pinipicture ko pa po 'yun isa-isa, 'yung module, 'yung pinaka-activity and then po 'yung answer sheet." (Yes, through *sisidlan* also. Then, there are students that prefer to do the modules earlier but what I do is like personal. Since we are friends and instead, they will have idle time, they want to do it already, so I send it to them. You just have to be patient ma'am. Then the other who don't have data for download, I take a picture of it one by one, the module, the activities only and then the answer sheet.)

3.1.6. Social Media

During the pandemic, social media played a big role in communicating and reaching the students. It was the only means to know them and monitor their progress in learning. Because other online platforms such as Google Classroom and Google Drive demanded so much from the students, teachers relied on social media, which almost all the students have. All of the teachers mentioned that they use social media to communicate with the students. Facebook and Messenger, the most popular social media, were used by the teachers. They used these to send to the students digitized copies of the modules and downloaded and self-made videos. Teachers have group conversations with the students where they can ask questions from the teachers about the modules. T7 shared how she used Facebook and Messenger to communicate and provide other instructional materials with the students. She said:

"Tapos aaaahhh, yung next naman, yung sa mga GC and Messenger natin. So sa GC naman, of course lahat naman ng section na hawak ko, like sa atin ang hawak ko ay 15 sections diba plus additional subject na dalawa, na dalawang section so 17. So lahat sila may GC. Yung common naman na ginagawa natin. And then lahat don inaupload ko na, instructions, digitized na, tawag dito, activity sheets. Basta lahat. Questions ng bata, question and answer, dun ko lahat pinupush. And then sa Messenger din through GC, dun ko din binibigay sa kanila yung mga possible na gagawin nila or mga assignment nila. Or kung may mga question sila, dun na lang din kami nagkequestion and answer. Pero merong mga time na merong nagpPM na bata so through Messenger din, minsan nagvivo call kami, kahit one on one to explain the instructions, kung anong laman ng ating lesson for that week. Kasi nga once a week ako so kailangan ay binibigay mo na talaga lahat ng kailangan nila. From GC, instruction muna and then sinesend ko na yung mga digitized copy nila." (Then, aaaahhh, next is the GC and Messenger. In the GC, of course, all the subjects that I handle, like in our school, I handle 15 sections plus 2 additional subjects, two sections so 17. So all of that has GC. That is the common thing that we do. And then I upload there instructions, digitized activity sheets. All of it. Questions of the students, question and answer, I do everything there. And then in the Messenger through the GC, I give to them the activities that they will possibly do or their assignments. Or if they have questions, we do the question and answer there. But there are times that students sent PM through Messenger also. Sometimes we do video call, even one on one to explain the instruction, the coverage of the lesson for that week. Because I am only once a week so I need to give everything to them. From GC, then instruction first, then I will send the digitized copy.)

Indeed, as an educational tool, social media enriched the learning experience by allowing students and instructors to exchange ideas, foster collaboration, and discussion, and engage and interact using such emerging social platforms (Lederer, 2012).

3.1.7. Online assessment tool

Aside from taking pictures of their answer sheets, two (2) teachers mentioned the use of web-based applications for assessing the students. They used Google Forms to get answers from the students. Google Forms was a cloud-based data management tool used for designing and developing web-based questionnaires. This tool was provided by Google Inc. and was freely available on the web to anyone to use and create web-based questionnaires. This tool helped the teachers to gather answers from the students and it automatically checks their work. T8 recalled that his students managed to answer their assessment through Google Forms. He said:

“Sa T___ po kasi, kinaya naman yung Google Forms kahit yung bata nakamodule. Kumbaga once lang naman yun. Baka yung bata nanghiram ng gadget.” (In T___, they managed Google Forms even the students who are in modular learning. For instance, it is only scheduled once. Maybe the students borrowed gadgets.)

T3, who also used Google Forms, revealed that all of his students managed to answer in the application. He recalled that he sets a time wherein students will go online and have load for the internet. He recalled:

“Hundred percent naman nakakapagsubmit sa Google Forms kasi nagseset lang talaga ako ng time para kung sakaling magload sila, talagang maaccomplish nila yun.” (Hundred percent of them can submit in Google Forms because I only set a time wherein when they load for data, they can accomplish it.)

3.1.8. Physical Activity Mobile Applications

Mobile applications for implementing physical activities (PA apps) were usually referred to as Physical Activity Mobile Applications. These applications allowed for the monitoring of the course of activities of various physical activities or sports through the sensor technologies integrated in mobile devices (Palicka, Jakubec & Zvonicek, 2016). For example, they measured path movement, distance, speed and the number of steps taken and with the use of simple algorithms they provided the user with a calorie counter relating to the activity selected (Nutriweb, 2013). One Physical Education teacher used a fitness application in one of her activities for the students.

3.1.9. Collaboration with teachers

Another modality that Physical Education teachers adopted was collaboration with other teachers. Two (2) teachers highlighted that collaborating and working with their co-teachers helped them to have the best modality in teaching Physical Education in this time of pandemic. T8 stated that his modality in teaching Physical Education during the pandemic had been a result of the collaboration with his co-teachers in senior high school. He said:

“Collaboration din po ito ng mga kasamahan ko sa SHS. Halimbawa may mga practices siya na maganda, isheshare niya yun hanggang sa marami na kaming nagagawa.” (It is also a collaboration of my colleagues in SHS. For example, if he/she has better practice, he/she will share it until most of us apply it already.)

3.2. Theme 2. Reasons in using the modalities

Another theme based from the interviews was the reasons of the Physical Education teachers in using the modalities they employed. The subthemes identified were student welfare and teacher convenience.

3.2.1. Student Welfare

Eight teachers (n=8) highlighted that they used the modalities because they take into consideration the welfare of their students. They wanted what is best for the students even in this time of pandemic. As teachers, they selflessly put the students' well-being first.

3.2.2. Students' Learning

Teachers were the ones who provide knowledge and guide the students to reach their full potential. Thus, the ultimate goal of Physical Education teachers was for the students to learn amidst the pandemic. Three teachers (n=3) shared that they used the modalities to help the students to gain understanding of their lesson in Physical Education.

3.2.3. Convenience of the students

One teacher (n=1), T3, mentioned that he used the modalities because it was more convenient for the students.

3.2.4. Encourage the students

T7 said that she used the modalities to encourage her learners. According to her, due to the pandemic, students needed more motivation; thus, the application of the different modalities in teaching Physical Education.

3.2.5. Teacher convenience

One Physical education teacher (n=1) shared a reason that is not similar to the rest of the group. It was revealed by T6. He said that he used these modalities to make it more convenient for the teachers. He said:

“Sa palagay ko yun po kasi yung convenient sa teacher, yung makapagsend ka ng video at makapagsend ng module online.” (I think that is because it is convenient for the teacher to send videos and module online.)

3.3. Theme 3. Challenges Encountered

Because of the pandemic, education was forced to adjust to the current situation. In the new normal set-up in teaching Physical Education, challenges were experienced by the teachers. These challenges may be classified as: personal (teacher and student), logistics and performance and assessment.

3.3.1. Personal (teacher)

Because of the changes in delivering instruction, Physical Education teachers experienced challenges such as checking outputs and lack of training and materials.

3.3.2. Checking of outputs

One teacher, T7, shared that she had a difficult time checking the outputs of her students. Due to the large number of students that she handled for Physical Education, checking their outputs was a challenge to her. She mentioned:

“Tapos checking of outputs. Yung sabi ko nga sa’yo kanina, so nakapag-isip ako ng strategy. Yung mga Google Forms, yun ba yung tawag dun, hindi kasi applicable sa kin. Napakadami kasi nila. Ang dami kong hawak na section. Parang ang hirap din.” (Then checking of outputs. Like what I told you earlier, so I thought of a strategy. Google Forms, is what you call it, it is not applicable to me. They are so many. I handle so many sections. It’s like difficult to do.)

3.3.3. Lack of training and materials

Because distance learning was new in our educational system, a lot of materials for the students and training for the teachers were not available. Teachers faced this school year without proper training to conduct online classes and materials were not ready to be given to the students. One teacher, T3, revealed that he experienced this challenge in teaching Physical Education. He said:

“Lack of training para iexecute kasi narinig ko sayo yung sabi mo, nagpapagamit ng fitness app. So ngayon ko naisip na, “Oo nga no. Pwede ako gumamit ng mga fitness app” Para makita din natin na they are performing ganyan. Lack of training din siguro para talaga magkaron ng mga idea how to deliver yung mga lessons.” (Lack of training to execute because I heard what you said, you use fitness app. And then I taught, Yes, I can also use fitness app. To see if they are really performing. I think maybe lack of training to have an idea on how to deliver the lessons.)

3.3.4. Personal (student)

Aside from the teachers, students also faced challenges in learning Physical Education during the pandemic. They lacked resources such as gadgets and load for internet connectivity.

3.3.5. Students’ Resources

Most of the students in the public schools cannot afford to have a stable internet connection at home. Thus, they resorted to connect on the internet using mobile data. This required good location for better network and budget to have load for the mobile data. All of the Physical Education teachers mentioned that poor or no internet connectivity of the students was one of the challenges they encountered. T9 shared that not all the students have the capacity to provide budget for the load of their mobile data every day. He shared:

“Saka yung pangload nila para sa internet. Hindi naman lahat kaya talaga na makapag-online. Minsan nga nakikipag-away pa sa magulang para magkaloal sila. Kaya yung ibang parents nagrereklamo.” (And also their load for the internet.

Not all can afford to go online. Sometimes, they argue with their parents just to have load. That is why some parents complain.)

T7 also revealed that since teachers are using online classes, internet connectivity has been a major problem. Due to lack of internet connectivity, she taught to a smaller number of students. She said:

“Syempre ngayon dahil online tayo, syempre number one is internet connectivity, yung internet connection. Ahhh, dahil, hindi naman tayo kagaya ng ibang lugar na nagpoprovide si division ng internet connection sa bawat lugar, so limited lang yung students na namimeet mo. So ang internet connection, pag walang connection, syempre less ang students na matuturuan mo.” (Because now we are online, of course, number one is internet connectivity, the internet connection. Ahhh, because we are not like the other places that the Division provides for the internet connection for their location, so you can only meet limited students. So internet connection, if there is no internet connection, of course you can only teach to less number of students.)

3.3.6. Communication with the students

Another problem that was identified by the Physical Education teachers was the difficulty in communicating with the students. Back then, communication with them was not a problem because the teachers and students were in the same place, the school. Teachers can easily update the students about their progress in learning and activities. Further, home visits were done by the teachers to those students who are always absent and never attends the class. But now, since we had distance learning due to the pandemic, teachers had difficulty reaching out to the students. Four teachers (n=4) mentioned that they find it difficult to communicate with their students.

3.3.7. Logistics

Since modular learning was implemented, teachers can get the outputs of the students through sisidlan (bags). Two (2) teachers mentioned that they had problems in using the sisidlan (bags). T8 revealed their struggles in getting the sisidlan when it was delivered in the school. He revealed:

“Maghahagilap ng papel sa sisidlan kasi pagdating nun disinfect din eh. Tatanggalin din sa lalagyan ganun.” (Finding papers in the sisidlan because when it arrives, it will be disinfected. The papers will be removed from it.)

3.3.8. Performance and Assessment

Due to the new set up in learning, teachers revealed that the attitude of the students was greatly affected. T3 shared that he does not feel the cooperation and willingness from his students. He shared:

“Tapos number 2, ‘yung cooperation nila, ‘yung willingness nila to do the performance task kasi nga this is something na they don’t usually do individually. Kasi minsan kapag pinag-sayaw mo sila in face-to-face they are group of 5, they are group of 10, but now they will do it alone so siguro ‘yung cooperation to do that. Mostly mga iyon, ‘yung mga gano’n.” (Then number 2, their cooperation, their willingness to do the performance task because this is something that they don’t usually do individually. Because sometimes when we instructed them to dance in face to face, they are grouped into 5, they are grouped into 10. But now, they will do it alone so I think the cooperation to that. Mostly that, like that.)

3.4. Theme 4. Solutions

To address the concerns, they encountered in teaching Physical Education, teachers thought of solutions to alleviate the problems they experience. Their solutions may be classified as personal, pedagogical, and social (parent involvement).

3.4.1. Personal

To overcome the challenges that Physical Education teachers encountered when it comes to materials and training, two (2) teachers shared they put effort in researching for materials and other strategies. T3 said that he researched for the materials he needed for his students. He said:

“Pangalawa, doon sa kulang mga materials natin syempre you will do some research in order for you to come up with the Learning Activity Sheets. So number 2 remedy ‘yun.” (Second, I do some research to suffice for the incomplete materials, in order for you to come up with the Learning Activity Sheets.)

3.4.2. Pedagogical

Teachers improvised ways to address the problems they experienced. Physical Education teachers used follow-up, more time allotment and providing opportunities as solutions pedagogically.

3.4.3. Follow-up

It was done to monitor the progress of the students. All of the Physical Education teachers shared that to address the concern of students who did not submit activities and performances, they communicated with the students to do a follow-up. T5 shared how he did the follow-up with the students. He said:

“Kapag yung mga bata hindi sila nakapagpasa para dun sa online learning materials and performances, as the subject teacher, tinatawagan ko sila isa-isa. Inaupdate ko sila sa dapat nilang gawin. Ineexplain ko yung process saka performances ng mga lesson.” (When the students did not submit for their online learning materials and performances, as the subject teachers, I call them one by one. I update them on what they need to do. I explain the process and performances of the lesson.)

3.4.4. Time Allotment

Giving more time for the students to submit their activities is another solution done by the teachers. Five (5) Physical Education teachers highlighted that giving more time was one of their remedies to address concerns in the submission of students' activities. T3 highlighted that he gives more time to the students because most of the students did not reach the deadline of submission. He said:

“Tapos number 3, nagbibigay lang ako ng grace period sa kanila kasi minsan we have set deadlines pero marami talagang students ang hindi nakaabot doon so siguro i'm making my time flexible for them to accomplish 'yung mga performance nila na ginagawa.” (Then number 3, I give grace period to them because sometimes, we have set deadlines but most of the students did not reach that. Maybe I am making my time flexible for them to accomplish the performances that they do.)

3.4.5. More Opportunities

Because modular learning was the main modality used in schools, the teachers believed that it was not enough for the students. Hence, they provided students with other ways of learning. Two (2) teachers mentioned that they used other means to teach the students. T1 shared that aside from modules and synchronous learning, she used other ways to help the students to learn Physical Education.

3.4.6. Social (parent involvement)

Another solution that teachers applied was involving the parents in the learning of the students. Since students were at home, they spent most of their time with their parents. Thus, involving them informed the teachers, as well as the parents, of the status of the students. Four teachers (n=4) revealed that they had involved the parents of their students who were inactive in their classes. T1 said that for the improvement of focus and cooperation of the students, she asked for the help of their parents. She said:

“Sa focus and cooperation naman nila, diyan na pumapasok yung tulong ng mga magulang satin para matuto yung mga anak. Kinakausap ko sila or kinocall ko yung attention nila regarding sa mga kulang na activities ng anak nila.” (For their focus and cooperation, I asked for the help of their parents so they can learn more. I talk or call their attention regarding the incomplete activities of their children.)

4. Conclusion

- Modular learning was the most common modality employed by Physical Education teachers during pandemic. Other modalities such as synchronous and asynchronous online learning and physical activity mobile applications were used by the teachers. The access of the students to these modalities depended on the availability of internet connection and gadgets. Further, collaboration with co-teachers was another mode done by the Physical Education teachers.
- During pandemic, teachers still prioritized the learning of the students. Their main reason in using the modalities was for the welfare of their students. However, one (1) teacher mentioned that he used these modalities for the convenience of the teachers.

- Lack of resources of students in terms of internet connectivity and gadgets was the common struggle experienced by the Physical Education teachers. Most of the public-school students cannot afford online learning. Due to this, even if Physical Education is a performance subject, teachers and students relied mostly on modular learning. Other challenges encountered by the Physical Education teachers were personal (teacher factor), logistics and performance and assessment.
- The most common solution done by the Physical Education teachers was doing follow-up with the students through social media. Since most of the students have accounts in social media, it was the easiest way to connect with them amidst the pandemic. Aside from doing follow-up, involving their parents, increased time allotment, providing more opportunities and teacher factors were identified as other solutions applied by Physical Education teachers.

Recommendations

- Though training for the teachers were done on how to deliver lessons in this time of pandemic, a specialized training for Physical Education teachers is needed so that they will have knowledge and skills on how to deliver lessons aside from using the modules. As a performance subject, the activities in Physical Education demand different expectations and teachers should be knowledgeable on how to design and prepare activities for performance besides letting students to answer the activities in the modules.
- The materials for Physical Education in Senior High School should be printed and provided to accommodate all the students. It will be less burden for the teachers because they will not allot time in making activity sheets. Thus, they can focus on how to deliver their lessons in Physical Education instead.
- Because Physical Education is viewed as one-hour teaching load in Senior High School, teachers need four sections to complete the four-hour teaching load per subject. Thus, Physical Education teachers commonly handle all the sections in Physical Education per grade level in senior high school. With that, principals and subject group heads should review the teaching load of the Physical Education teachers to help them ease the burden in collecting and checking of students' outputs and grading the students.
- The use of DepEd TV should be strengthened in Physical Education. The lessons in Physical Education that are scheduled to be televised should be aligned with the modules used by the teachers. Further, it should be coordinated with the teachers so that they can use it in their lessons and students can watch and learn from it.
- Parents/ guardians should have a more active involvement in the learning of their children in this time of pandemic since they stay mostly at home. Parents are the partners of teachers, and they serve as facilitator of learning at home. Parents should establish a connection, guide their children in learning the lessons and the provide the resources the students need because the involvement of parents have a great impact on the success of distance learning.
- Future researchers may investigate the same variables in other subjects to find out if the results would be the same. Since the study also focused on Grades 11 and 12 teachers, teachers in Junior High School may also be included in the future studies to check whether the same modalities are applied by the teachers in Junior High School.
- Schools may be encouraged to adopt the proposed action plan to improve the modalities of teachers in teaching Physical Education and to help them avoid problems they may encounter.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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